

NIVA WP 3 –ZLTO interview

Date: 08 October 2020 - 16h 30 – 18 h

Location: Teams meeting

Stakeholder description

1. Organisation name: ZLTO
2. Person name: removed for privacy reasons
3. Person position /role : project manager; activities include European topics
4. What is the general purpose of the organisation?

ZLTO is a farmer organisation (around 40 000 farmers in South Holland); main purposes are lobby, advise and innovation

5. What are the activities related to agriculture in general ? What are the activities requiring use of data about agriculture?

ZLTO is providing a free tool that is using data about agriculture. This tool is mainly used by farmers (for their own farm management), by advisers and by cooperatives (for their ordering system).

User experience – User requirements

1. What current IACS data do you need?

- Parcels with their land use

We need the agricultural parcel geometry and the crop type that is provided using the AgroConnect standard. We don't display the parcel identifier.

The parcel layer is used as a BaseMap used as background to locate or link lots of other information. For instance, we also display cadastral parcels.

Farmers are interested by data about their neighbours parcels for land transfer. For instance, to comply with crop rotation rules, they often have to rent various parcels according the agricultural campaign and their production plans. There is also need of some specific soil for fruit trees and/or nurseries.

Advisers are interested by this layer of agricultural parcels that is necessary to understand clearly which parcel the farmer is talking about, to avoid mistakes.

Cooperatives are interested as they want to know what the farmer has to deliver. The layer of agricultural parcels may be combined with growth data (coming from satellites) at various moments of the year ; this enables to forecast the harvest.

ZLTO is not yet aggregated data or making statistics but it is in project for next years; it would be useful for the lobby work.

We have had data on agricultural parcels since 2009. Data is globally updated once a year. In case of smaller changes, we receive the update automatically (with a small delay – about one day).

- LPIS data

We also use Reference Parcels (mainly to check that agricultural parcels are within reference parcels), agricultural areas and EFA. The cultivated EFA (e.g. catch crops) are considered in a similar way as agricultural parcels whereas the landscape feature (trees, ponds ...) are mainly used as landmarks on the map.

- Animals

It is also important. We need it for legislation: to get new permits, we should show how animals were kept. We need data at least from the past 5 years.

We have this information, there are viewers, it is not only in RVO but also elsewhere.

- Beneficiaries

We also need this information but it is submitted to farmer authorization.

This information would be useful for cooperatives to deliver supplies, for instance to assess or to know the required seeds. Currently, it is difficult to get exact information, there are often some parcels forgotten.

Insurance companies want to make requests by farmer identifier.

- Quality controls

It is currently not open. ZLTO understands that RVO can't share anything about its internal procedures of quality checks but farmers and their advisers would like to make it more transparent, to get more information.

- Entitlements

ZLTO is not aware if such system exists in Netherlands.

- Payments

Data is currently not publicly available. It may be made open in very specific cases (e.g. for Court of Justice).

Some environmental NGO want this data to be open (to check if public money is rightly spent) but ZLTO current position is against publication: don't make it too easy to complain against farmers! This position might evolve in future.

2. What potential future IACS data do you need?

- Farm holding (Farm Registry)

Expected information is more or less the same as current information on beneficiaries. But globally, we agree on the principle that Farm concept is important.

- Crop plots (Farm Registry)

Every one (farmers, farmer organisation, suppliers or distributors) would be interested to get best possible details.

- Farm plans (Seamless Claim)

Yes, this would be interesting for social aspects. Currently, various suppliers (fertilizers, crop protection product) have their own database but this could change: if farm plans were publicly available, farmers could have only one field plan for contacting various suppliers; it would enable them to raise some competition between suppliers.

However, it is to be communicated with care; it might be difficult.

- Crop classification (EO monitoring)

In Netherland, this information is already provided by WUR that is doing good job. They ensure good persistency in providing this service and data is continuously updated (a priori, a new crop map at each new visit by satellites).

- Traffic lights (EO monitoring)

Yes, it would be useful for farmers to get this information. It would increase transparency.

- Geotagged photos

Netherland has not yet implemented the new monitoring system therefore ZLTO is poorly aware about geo-tagged photos but, a priori, rather in favour of using and publishing them in order to bring clarity on farmer activity, to show accurately how he or she works.

- Agro-environmental indicators

In general, ZLTO is in favour of making these indicators publicly available. This would show to the farmers that they are on good track, to make them confident: be good and tell it!

Carbon budget is important for soil health and fertility and for climate change mitigation. There is a project in Netherlands.

Nitrate lixiviation indicator might be used to convince government to make more tailored regulations, i.e. according to regional context (crop rotation, farm organisation).

There are also some initiatives in Netherlands about biodiversity but it is quite a complex topic. However if good indicators are possible (even at proxy level), farmers should have them and know their individual contribution.

Opinion about data sharing principles

1. What data do you think should be publicly available for use?

There are different levels of “publicly available”; it is not a “yes/no” answer. For instance, payments may be publicly available with farmer authorization.

2. What data do you think should not be shared and should only be used by Paying Agencies?

- What has made you feel this way/why do you think this way?

Internal control mechanisms can't be shared completely but it would be nice to share a bit better or earlier some results to ensure transparency.

Farmers are willing to know as soon as possible if they will get payment and on time.

3. Who do you think most benefits from partially or open data sharing?

- Can you explain why you feel this way?

Mainly the farmers and the network around farmers (including farmer associations). We have to make farmers happy to share data.

4. Do you have any idea about how the process of data sharing from farmer to wider stakeholder groups can be improved?

There are 3 categories of data: open, available if authorization, close.

The most promising solution is to make easier the authorization process (for farmers). There is a project in Netherlands on this topic.

For instance, currently, farmers may declare a damage (e.g. too much rain) to insurance companies by clicking on the concerned parcel and its crop but this may be done only if farmer contacts PA and authorize insurance companies. Farmer will have similar procedure to do to provide authorization to farmer cooperative for dairy analysis.

The idea would be to offer farmers a “box” where they can manage authorizations in one place.